

Workshop Summary

“Towards Implementation of the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science – How to integrate citizen science into (open) science policy”

Online workshop jointly organised by the Citizen Science & Open Science Community of Practice and the UNESCO Natural Sciences Sector

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Workshop agenda

1. Welcome & Opening - Dr. Uta Wehn (IHE Delft, NL), workshop moderator
2. Welcome from UNESCO - Dr. Lutz Moeller (German Commission for UNESCO)
3. Setting the scene - Libby Hepburn (Australian CS Association, CS Global Partnership)
 - UNESCO’s perspective - Dr. Ana Persic (UNESCO)
 - JRC perspective - Dr. Sven Schade (Joint Research Centre, EC)
 - EU perspective - Gabriella Leo (EU Commission)
 - NL perspective - Margaret Gold (CS Lab, University of Leiden, NL)
 - US perspective - Dr. Alison Parker (Wilson Center, USA)
4. Q&A
 - Interactive session
 - Discussion
5. Wrap up and next steps - Dr. Tiffany Straza (UNESCO)

Minutes

1. Welcome & Opening - Dr. Uta Wehn (IHE Delft, NL)

Session opened by Uta Wehn and Libby Hepburn – session co-hosted by the CS OS CoP and UNESCO. Agenda introduced.

2. Welcome from UNESCO - Dr. Lutz Moeller (German Commission for UNESCO)

Essentials of [UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science](#) were introduced – it is a text of international law, developed through a participatory process of consensus building (giving it a strong legitimacy). It has already played an important role in many countries, modernising the understanding of science, research integrity and assessment. For example, in Germany the commission for UNESCO has promoted the result of the recommendations, and forums will be held to advance open science (OS).

Opening science means opening up science: between scientists, across borders, between disciplines, and towards society and policy. The Recommendation considers open science as an umbrella concept, for example allowing actors working in open data to work with actors working in citizen science.

Citizen science is seen as a form of open engagement, but **citizen science (CS) has not yet been integrated into policy and practice in the Recommendations (in great detail)**. There is a lot of work to be done here, and this is what this workshop is contributing to.

3. Setting the scene - Libby Hepburn (Australian CS Association, CS Global Partnership)

CS OS CoP set up to support the development of the Recommendations – we are now in the implementation phase. 5 OS working groups established:

- Capacity building
- Policies and Policy Instruments
- Funding and Incentives
- Infrastructures
- Monitoring Framework

CoP members are involved in each of the working groups, but it became evident that elements focusing on opening science to society received little attention (despite 50% of Recommendation themes concerning this issue). When challenging UNESCO on this, they agreed and threw the challenge back to us, to create a resource of CS examples and guidance by 6 December 2022 (World Science Forum).

Three themes:

1. Creating a common functional vocabulary and conceptualisation of open engagement with societal actors and historically underrepresented knowledge systems
2. Showcasing practice examples of success: What do supportive enabling conditions look like? What does a successful initiative look like, in which context? Examples of citizen science in policy (particularly at the national level)
3. Identifying principles for initiating, nurturing/sustaining and monitoring open engagement/citizen science

A call for contributors was sent out – we now have 55 registrations from 27 countries.

Objectives of this workshop:

- Share experiences and lessons learned on opening science to society via (open science) policy
- Identify needs of policy makers for progressing citizen science into (open) science policy, as input for the UNESCO OS working group on policy

UNESCO's perspective - Dr. Ana Persic (UNESCO)

This process is very important, and makes the Recommendation livelier and more relevant to OS actors. UNESCO is counting on feedback during the process.

UNESCO Recommendation on OS was developed due to the need for an international policy and action framework, nor was there a common definition of OS, or a shared set of values or principles. The Recommendation aims to do exactly this. UNESCO was tasked to develop the Recommendation by member states in 2019. Following a participatory process, involving negotiations from member states, it was unanimously adopted.

Highlights:

- First international normative instrument on OS
- Contains first internationally agreed definition of OS
- Spells out consensus core values and guiding principles of OS
- Addresses multiple actors and stakeholders of OS
- Recommends action on different levels to operationalise OS principles
- Proposes innovative approaches for OS at different stages of the scientific cycle
- Calls for development of a comprehensive OS monitoring framework

Recommendation gives 7 key areas of action:

- Promoting a common understanding of OS
- Development of enabling policy environment
- Investing in infrastructure and services
- Investing in training, education, digital literacy etc for OS
- Fostering a culture of OS and aligning incentives for OS
- Promoting innovative approaches to OS
- Promoting international and multi-stakeholder cooperation in the context of OS

Key challenges for Recommendation implementation:

- Capacity building
- Policies
- Financing
- Infrastructure
- Monitoring

As Libby mentioned, working groups have been developed to help overcome some of these challenges – input is needed for this.

More on the implementation process [here](#).

Some of these tools and guidelines will be promoted at the World Science Forum on Open Science Day (7 Dec 2022).

JRC perspective - Dr. Sven Schade (Joint Research Centre, EC)

This presentation focused on environmental citizen science, from a European perspective. JRC is an in-house scientific knowledge centre for the European Commission, bridging the interface between science and policy. CS is part of the knowledge informing environment related policy making.

CS classical steps (e.g. collection, quality control etc) interconnected with policy processes. Once a policy is put into place, CS can be used to monitor impacts (in a cyclical manner). Has been used to monitor invasive species etc. This scheme could be applied at a range of levels (local, national, international etc).

In 2017, a fitness check for environmental reporting and monitoring was conducted, leading to an action plan – a key action was to promote the use of CS. A study on CS for environmental policy and monitoring was conducted, and stakeholder input was gathered. In 2020, the best practices in CS for environmental monitoring were developed.

A follow up activity was to ensure uptake by environmental protection agencies, who provided a response to the recommendations, outlining how the recommendations could be made actionable by agencies. This work is also being conducted with national mapping agencies, national statistics offices etc.

Useful links from the presentation: [overview report](#); [2020 recommendations](#), [group of environmental protection agencies in Europe](#) (managed by EEA).

EU perspective - Gabriella Leo (EU Commission)

This presentation gave an overview of how the EU Commission integrated CS in OS R&I policy.

Pact for R&I in Europe – developed after 20 years of policy support, and enforces the political basis for action in citizen and societal engagement and CS. OS is central to the values, principles and priorities of the Pact.

After a long process, in 2020 a new ERA policy agenda of the EC was developed – CS is one of the eight pillars of the OS policy part of this agenda.

The role of CS in decision making has been growing across Europe – the EC launched the Multi Learning Exercise (MLE) of CS to strengthen CS national policies and initiatives, and to upscale cross-national CS initiatives. The forthcoming final report will detail recommendations, lessons learned and best practice across Europe.

Progress towards CS policy initiatives is linked with dedicated funding programmes (e.g. H2020-Swafs projects). At programme level, EC have been supporting citizen and societal engagement (incl. CS) through Horizon Europe, which supports a multi-actor approach (e.g. through co-creation, co-design etc).

NL perspective - Margaret Gold (CS Lab, University of Leiden, NL)

This presentation gave the Dutch perspective on how CS is being embedded in OS policy.

At the national level, OS is traditionally top-down and university-driven, but is now becoming broader, with various perspectives included. The UNESCO Recommendations led to a new strategy for how the Netherlands understands OS.

Strategic goals (for 2030):

- Close collaboration between actors in research processes (with citizens contributing and benefiting)
- Inclusive, efficient and transparent processes of co-creation, evaluation, quality assurance and communication
- Removal of barriers to reading and reusing scientific output
- Products of and for knowledge creation being findable accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)

Thinking has shifted: three previous programme lines (Fair Data, Open Access and Citizen Science) have been reframed through a consultation process. UNESCO definition of societal engagement and

participation being embraced, and more practices are being captured. Four key lines of action (NPOS rolling agenda) have emerged:

- Towards societal engagement and participation (largely where CS fits)
- Towards inclusive and transparent scientific processes
- Towards open scholarly communication
- Towards FAIR and open research outputs

Grassroots movements in the Netherlands campaigned for CS to be part of the wider OS picture, this was a community movement (through continuous feedback). Key to this was the development of the national CS network.

Key to discussion in the Netherlands was conversation on rewards and recognition – understanding various types of value, beyond simple impact factor (e.g. team science etc).

MLE (mentioned by Gabriella) have been important in shaping this – report on enabling environments may be of particular interest. Work in the [WeObserve](#) project also had a big role in informing how this work took shape.

Workshop slides are [here](#) and the EU Mutual Learning Exercise on Citizen Science repository of reports is [here](#).

US perspective - Dr. Alison Parker (Wilson Center, USA)

This presentation outlined current events and progress in the US with regards to CS OS policy (at the Federal level).

White House memo in 2015 focused on addressing science and society challenges through citizen science approaches. This memo was significant, drafting core principles (data quality, fitness for use, openness, meaningful public participation). Various resources for practitioners of CS and crowdsourcing were then developed. In 2016 a bill provided general authorisation of the use of CS within the government.

Within the EPA, an advisory council provided recommendations for the use of CS for environmental protection. A report from the Office of the Inspector General highlighted the need for a comprehensive strategy for CS.

More recent outputs and developments:

- Publication of CS Quality Assurance & Documentation Handbook from EPA
- NASA TOPS (Transform to Open Science)
- NOAA CS Strategy
- OSTP initiatives (focusing on opening science to society)

4. Q&A

The Q&A section covered a range of topics. The monitoring of the impact of investment in CS was discussed (particularly with regards to increased investment in the EU), breaking CS out of its silo in environment to other sectors (e.g. health), as well as the importance of using policy to reduce the number of gatekeepers to smaller scale citizen science practitioners (particularly when accessing funding).

An in depth discussion also took place on the various mechanisms and platforms that are being used to solicit public feedback or engagement on methodologies. Margaret Gold highlighted the limitations of traditional (roundtable) approaches to soliciting feedback from large groups, while Alison Parker mentioned several platforms used in the USA ([Challenge.gov](https://www.challenge.gov/) (an ideation platform) and the [traditional federal register](#)).

Interactive session & Discussion

Interactive [Miro session](#) introduced. Participants added comments to a 'Policy Makers' Needs Canvas' to highlight the tasks of policy makers for including societal actors in OS policy, the gains (benefits expected from OS policies) and pains (current issues experienced by policy makers).

During the interactive session, several discussions took place. Solving the various administrative and logistical issues of funding (intellectual investment funds, requiring detailed proposals) from the policy makers side was a key point of discussion, with the suggestion that funding should be available for CS in all relevant calls (not just those specific for CS) as a default. It was also suggested that room for experimentation (in terms of CS approach) should be allowed within funding, in order to support innovative approaches (e.g. co-design with local authorities). A further discussion point centred around the recent reform research assessment, and the possibilities that such an approach (looking beyond impact factor and # of publications) offers for CS.

The importance of awareness raising and communication (beyond the CS bubble) was also highlighted, in order to share the potential of CS to increase availability and accessibility of information to non-experts. In CS it seems that there is an understanding of the roles in environmental sciences, but beyond this there is little understanding. We need to showcase the examples from environment to other sectors, to teach other disciplines about the potential of CS. The UNESCO working groups offer a pathway to get involved here.

Issues associated with “Invisible Citizen Science” (initiatives that don’t get noticed within institutional settings) were also discussed. If we wish to support citizen-led citizen science, they are spontaneous in nature and hard to grab.

5. Wrap up and next steps - Dr. Tiffany Straza (UNESCO)

OS is a movement that involves bottom up action that is already being done (e.g. within CS). There is also a top-down effort to support this action.

OS means opening up in outputs of science, and also in the process of conducting and creating science. Countries are therefore looking for guidance.

Key thoughts on the presentations and discussions today:

- We still need to bolster a common understanding of CS (e.g. moving beyond the understanding of CS as simply a data gathering effort). The CS Global Partnership can help facilitate connections around the world for this effort.
- There is a need to create entry points for the CS community to engage with the policy process, and to create contact points with the amount of people ready to give inputs. Engagement can be integrated throughout the OS process.
- Practical support is required (including funding). We shouldn’t perceive citizens as a blank slate, but as a group with a variety of specialised skills who can contribute to the whole of the scientific process.
- The examples that we heard from today are from relatively resource rich contexts. We also need to connect with areas that are less resource rich, to find out what they are already doing, or support the introduction of this work in these contexts.
- How do we tackle this work across sectors? Some are more advanced than others.
- How do we track impacts of investments that we make? From the perspectives of IP, how can we give credit to work that is already being done and avoid duplication.

Next steps:

- The CS OS CoP is putting together guidance for supporting open engagement with societal actors to bolster the aspect of OS globally.
- At UNESCO, guidance is being created for policy makers looking to implement the UNESCO Recommendations (including a variety of short documents).
- Stay in touch via the CS OS CoP and UNESCO Working Groups

At UNESCO, there are [five Working Groups](#) tackling the priority challenges facing the implementation of the Recommendation on Open Science. Anyone is welcome to join at any time, just register for a meeting or email openscience@unesco.org.

To stay in touch about citizen science: Participants are very welcome to join the Community of Practice on Citizen Science & Open Science, at which policy aspects are regularly (but not exclusively) discussed: please sign up [here](#). You can also reach out to info@globalcitizenscience.org and take a look at <http://globalcitizenscience.org/>.